

MODE I, MODE II AND FIXED RATIO MIXED I/II FATIGUE DELAMINATION OF DIFFERENT CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

For composite design, it is desirable to have data covering the failure envelope from Mode I to Mode II. The existing standard procedures for quasi-static testing (ISO 15024 for Mode I and ISO 15114 for Mode II) have recently been shown to be adaptable for the respective fatigue tests under displacement control in round robin tests performed by Technical Committee 4 of the European Structural Integrity Society. The Calibrated End-Loaded Split (C-ELS) test set-up developed for Mode II as described in the ISO standard further allows to perform a Fixed-Ratio Mixed Mode I/II (FRMM) test by simply inverting the loading direction compared to mode II. This test is now explored with quasi-static and fatigue loading for selected carbon fibre reinforced polymer-matrix (CFRP) composite laminates. Recent fatigue delamination analysis showed that a modified Hartman-Schijve approach can be used to achieve power law representations of fatigue crack growth in composites with exponents of around 2. This is significantly lower than the exponent values seen for composites with the common Paris law data representation that can amount to values in the range between about 3 and 10. Thus, the modified Hartman-Schijve approach may yield data for a damage tolerant design philosophy requiring the assessment of delamination growth in composite structures. Based on these findings, the applicability of this data representation approach to various CFRP composite laminates is investigated. Cyclic FRMM I/II tests were carried out and analysed with both, the common Paris law and the modified Hartman-Schijve approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

Experimental investigations of the delamination behaviour and research into defining test procedures for reproducibly characterizing the fracture toughness or delamination resistance of fibre reinforced polymer-matrix (FRP) composite laminates have been performed for more than 50 years [1,2]. Concurrent with the experimental work, also modelling and simulation was used for understanding the delamination behaviour (see, e.g., [3] for a summary). In spite of these significant efforts, only a limited number of test standards has been published yet [4]. Most of the published test standards address quasi-static loading in one of the basic modes, or for selected mixed mode combinations [5–10]. The only standard test procedure on cyclic fracture fatigue is characterizing delamination onset under mode I loading in the near threshold regime [11]. There are, however, round

robin activities in preparing cyclic fatigue standards for FRP composite laminates under various loading modes and published research (see, e.g., [4] for details).

Test development for standardisation of mixed mode I/II fracture toughness of FRP composites still has to solve technical problems, on one hand the question of mode partitioning for quasi-static and cyclic fatigue mixed mode I/II tests with arbitrary ratios of mode I and mode II [12–16], and on the other, data analysis and interpretation of the tests for the different modes, see, e.g. [17–19] for a discussion of the issues and problems. One advantage of the fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II test discussed here is that the mode partitioning is not debated; it is a ratio of 4:3 for mode I to mode II [12]. Besides the specification of the test procedures and of the analysis of the data, an important issue is the use of the data obtained from the tests, i.e., the scope of the procedure. Since most of the standard tests require unidirectional fibre-reinforcement which is rarely used in applications, their main areas of application are envisaged in quality control and comparative material selection. Research indicates that changing to cross-ply or multi-directional FRP laminates may result in fracture behaviour that violates some of the basic assumptions in the test standards, e.g., by deviation of the delamination from the mid-plane of the test specimen [20] or by splitting or multiple delaminations propagating parallel in several interlaminar planes [21,22].

The use of cyclic fracture fatigue data in design of composite structures or elements is not state-of-the-art yet, even though the basic methodology has been established (see, e.g., [23]). Typically, aircraft and other composite structures or elements are still designed considering strength and stiffness criteria only, one of the few published exceptions is helicopter rotor flexbeams [24,25]. The data analysis of cyclic fatigue fracture is frequently based on the so-called Paris-law [26] which is a double-logarithmic plot of delamination length increment per cycle (da/dN) as a function of applied stress (usually maximum energy release rate G_{max} for the respective mode or the difference between maximum and minimum, denoted ΔG). The slope of these curves is fairly steep (amounting to values between about 3 and 10) and hence very sensitive to small variations in applied stress. Hence, if cyclic fracture fatigue data are being used for design, this is based on the so-called threshold values G_{thr} , below which apparently no delamination propagation will occur. Recently, an approach for data analysis that had been originally developed for metals [27] has been transferred to FRP composites [28,29]. The double-logarithmic graph of da/dN versus stress level from the modified Hartman-Schijve equation yields slopes that are lower than those from the Paris-law and hence are possibly better suited to yield design data. Also, the G_{thr} value is an explicit parameter in the equation and can hence be determined from a fitting of the data. As shown by recent analysis of epoxy adhesive fatigue fracture data, the modified Hartman-Schijve equation yields a master curve type of data fitting independent of the stress ratio R [30]. Therefore, the data analysis presented in this manuscript will explore the applicability of the modified Hartman-Schijve equation for data analysis and threshold value determination from fixed-ratio cyclic fracture fatigue tests under mixed mode I/II loading, extending the first literature study by Jones et al. [29].

2 MATERIALS AND TEST PROCEDURE

The present contribution presents and discusses selected results from quasi-static and cyclic fatigue fracture testing performed at the authors' laboratories in exploring the feasibility of a mixed mode I/II cyclic fatigue fracture test procedure based on the so-called "inverted" C-ELS test, i.e., the mode II quasi-static test described in [6] but with the loading direction inverted.

Two different carbon-fibre reinforced polymer-matrix (CFRP) composite laminate types have been investigated. The fibres include AS4 and IM7, and the matrix polymers were epoxies (977-2 and 8552). The specimens were beam-like, nominally 20 mm wide, about 3-4 mm thick (depending on the CFRP-type) and between about 150 mm and 200 mm long. The crack started from a laminated insert film, typically a fluorinated polymer, with a thickness between about 10 and 25 micrometer. It can be noted that 13 micrometer or less is the required thickness for quasi-static fracture testing in most standards, but since cyclic fatigue starts from a quasi-static precrack, the thickness of the insert film is not expected to have a direct effect on the results. Some effects of precracking or crack starter on cyclic fatigue delamination propagation cannot be excluded, however, see, e.g., [31] for details on the relevant mechanisms. Fibre-bridging is an important effect, mainly in unidirectionally reinforced FRP

composites [31], and recently, modelling has been used to assess this for mode I loading, but this will also be relevant for mixed mode I/II loading to some degree [32].

Preliminary testing first indicated that the quasi-static procedure yielded sufficiently consistent results for the FRP composite laminates tested at different laboratories and then the quasi-static test procedure was used as a basis for defining a cyclic fracture fatigue test. The test procedure defined test frequencies between about 1 and 10 Hz (the upper limit was set because of possible self-heating of the laminates), displacement control (because of problems observed when load control was used in mode I cyclic fatigue tests, see [33] for details), and a compliance based data analysis using machine load records for both, determining the effective crack length (see, e.g., [34] for further details on this) and the stress level (analogous to the approach used for earlier mode I cyclic fracture fatigue tests [19]). This approach eliminates the operator-dependent visual observation of crack or delamination length that is rather subjective and cannot be reanalysed (unless the delamination propagation is recorded on video). An important point is the load recording, detailed analysis of data from cyclic fracture fatigue tests under mode I loading indicated that sufficiently low load cell ranges have to be used to avoid significant scatter in the lower da/dN and stress range [19]. A possible alternative (but not yet investigated in detail) could be suitable averaging of machine load and displacement data, maybe using a sliding average increasing with increasing cycle number. Unless the averaging is defined a priori, recording all data points, i.e., every cycle, for a post-test evaluation of averaging approaches will result in large data files which may not be optimal for a standard test procedure. In developing the test procedure, however, this will be investigated in the round robin and provide a suitable averaging with sufficiently low scatter. It has to be further noted that additional requirements may have to be implemented into the procedure for obtaining reproducible results with acceptable in- and inter-laboratory scatter. Pending data analysis from round robin testing is currently under preparation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to show the benefits, but also the possible limitations of the modified Hartman-Schijve fitting for cyclic fracture fatigue testing under fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II loading, selected test data from CFRP composite laminates are presented in the following sections. First, the values obtained from quasi-static mixed mode I/II tests that serve as reference for the upper limit of fatigue tests are presented (Section 3.1). Section 3.2 then presents and discusses the cyclic fracture data obtained from fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II loading.

3.1 Quasi-static fixed-ratio mixed-mode I/II testing

Table 1 summarizes the quasi-static initiation values obtained for selected CFRP composite laminates subjected to fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II loading. In spite of the limited statistics (no information on inter-laboratory scatter), the different types of CFRP can be distinguished. As expected, the mixed-mode I/II data with a ratio of 4:3 of mode I to mode II lie between the conservative (lower bound) mode I and the higher mode II values. The nominal mixed mode I/II value calculated with a ratio of 4:3 from the respective single mode data (mode I and mode II) agrees reasonably well with the value measured directly.

Laminate type	$G_{I/II}$ total [J/m ²]	G_I DCB [J/m ²]	G_{II} C-ELS [J/m ²]	$G_{I/II}$ calc [J/m ²]
IM7/977-2	*	333 [35]	994 [35]	616
AS4/8552	579	266	1082 [36]	616

Table 1: Initiation values from quasi-static fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II testing of selected CFRP laminates. Mixed mode values were calculated from Mode I and Mode II data (* no data available).

3.2 Cyclic fracture fatigue fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II testing

The data from cyclic fatigue fracture under fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II loading for IM7/977-2 and AS4/8552 are summarized in Figure 1 (a) and (b), respectively. The symbols represent the measured data calculated via Corrected Beam Theory (CBT). Lines show results predicted via the modified Hartman-Schijve approach.

Table 2 gives the parameters used for predicting the fatigue crack growth behaviour via the modified Hartman-Schijve as shown in Figure 1. While for IM7/977-2 no monotonic fixed ratio mode I/II data was available (instead, the calculated value was used), for AS4/8552 the measured monotonic mixed mode I/II data was used as value for the parameter A. For both, IM7/977-2 and AS4/8552, β was fixed to 4. All other parameters were chosen so that they best represent the experimental data.

The comparison of the fatigue crack growth behaviour of IM7/977-2 and AS4/8552 is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 (a) shows the measured values in a Paris type data representation and Figure 2 (b) the same data represented via a modified Hartman-Schijve approach.

Figure 1: Selected cyclic fracture fatigue data from testing CFRP laminates under fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II, data analysis is performed using the Paris-law type presentation and machine compliance values.

Material	A [J/m ²]	β [-]	D [mm/cycle * (J/m ²) ^(-n/2)]	G _{thr} [J/m ²]
IM7/977-2	616	4	6e-7	90
AS4/8552	579	4	3e-8	80

Table 2: Values for the parameters of the modified Hartman-Schijve approach. A is a toughness like parameter, G_{th} a threshold like parameter, β the exponent of the Hartman-Schijve equation and D a constant in the Hartman-Schijve equation.

Figure 2: Comparison of cyclic fracture fatigue IM7/977-2 and AS4/8552 data from testing under fixed-ratio mixed mode I/II. Data analysis is performed using the Paris-law type presentation (a) and modified Hartman-Schijve type presentation (b).

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Mixed mode I/II data for both IM7/977-2 and AS4/8552 are shown in this paper. Monotonic mixed mode testing was carried out for AS4/8552 and compared to values calculated from mode I and mode II data. The results yield comparable values for both the measured and the estimated monotonic mixed mode I/II data. The measured monotonic mixed mode I/II data was used as input parameter for the analysis of fatigue data via the modified Hartman-Schijve approach.

The fitting parameter A for IM7/977-2 was set to 616 [J/m²], the calculated mixed mode toughness value. For AS4/8552, the measurement of $G_{I/IIc}$ yielded a value of 579 [J/m²] and is thus lower than the calculated monotonic mixed mode I/II data, which amounts to 616 [J/m²]. The measured value was used as input parameter for the parameter A in the modified Hartman-Schijve approach. This yielded a prediction of the fatigue crack growth behaviour with reasonable good agreement with the measured mixed mode I/II data in the Paris plot. Since the exponent β was fixed to four, two parameters (D and G_{thr}) needed to be adapted to agree with the measured data.

Both Paris type and modified Hartman-Schijve data representation of fatigue data was shown. Data analysis yields significant differences in the fatigue behaviour of these two types of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites under cyclic mixed mode I/II loading. Still, the predicted threshold values are similar for both materials and amount to around 80 and 90 J/m² for AS4/8552 and IM7/977-2, respectively.

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